

Diagnosis, grading and management of chelonian shell fractures in exotic animal practice

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ABSTRACT

With the recent trends in domestication of chelonian species, the incidences of shell fractures of multi-factorial etiology are one of the most commonly presented conditions. Multiple invasive and non-invasive treatment modalities are available for the shell fracture fixation. The methods range from adhesives to bone plates. Novel techniques like vacuum assisted closure, photodynamic therapy and platelet-rich plasma are also available for hastened healing and reduced complications. This article deals with the diagnosis, grading and management of chelonian shell fractures.

KEYWORDS: Carapace, chelonian, plastron, shell fracture, trauma, turtle

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